

Stability Constants and Thermodynamic Functions of Humic and Fulvic Acid Complexes with Fe(III), Al(III), Mo(VI), V(IV) and Ti(IV)

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Stability constants of Fe(III), Al(III), Mo(VI), V(IV) and Ti(IV) complexes of humic and fulvic acids were determined by Resin exchange method⁵ at two different temperatures and thermodynamic functions of the complexes are evaluated therefrom.

FE(III), Al(III) etc. are known to form complexes with humic (HA), fulvic (FA) and hyatomelanolic acid (HyA) fractions of soil organic matter¹⁻⁴. Stability constants for HyA-metal complexes obtained by Resin exchange method⁵ have been reported⁶. In the present paper the stability constant values for some other metal-complex e.g., Mo(VI), V(IV) and Ti(IV) complexes are reported. In this connection attempts have also been made to evaluate some thermodynamic functions of the complexes so as to get an idea about the nature of such interactions.

Experimental

Soil organic matter fractions e.g., humic (HA), fulvic (FA) and hyatomelanolic (HyA) have been extracted, fractionated and purified from Chinsura soil, West Bengal by usual procedure⁵. For determination of stability constant (log K) values of different fractions of soil organic matter-metal combinations, the same procedure as discussed earlier⁶ has been adopted. In all the cases log K values have been determined at two different temperatures of 30° and 40° ± 0.5 maintained by thermostatic bath. In order to derive the thermodynamic parameters, the following relationships have been used

$$\Delta G = -RT \ln K \quad \dots (1)$$

$$\frac{d \ln K}{dT} = \frac{\Delta H}{RT^2} \quad \dots (2)$$

$$\Delta G = \Delta H - T \Delta S \quad \dots (3)$$

Results and Discussion

The stability constant (log K) values for various systems along with their free energy of formation

(ΔG), enthalpy change (ΔH) and entropy changes (ΔS) are summarised in Tables (1-4).

TABLE-1 STABILITY CONSTANTS OF METAL ORGANIC MATTER COMBINATION

Soil organic matter fraction	Metal ion	T=30°C log K ₁	T=40°C log K ₂
HA	Fe(III)	3.56	3.79
	Al(III)	3.15	3.38
	V(IV)	5.90	7.00
	Ti(IV)	5.30	6.30
	Mo(VI)	7.10	8.40
FA	Fe(III)	5.28	6.00
	Al(III)	5.44	5.60
	Vi(IV)	6.30	7.50
	Ti(IV)	5.80	6.90
	Mo(VI)	7.60	9.00
HyA	Fe(III)	3.97	4.93
	Al(III)	3.81	3.88
	V(IV)	4.10	5.00
	Ti(IV)	3.80	4.50
	Mo(VI)	5.60	6.60

TABLE-2 FREE ENERGY (ΔG), ENTHALPY (ΔH) AND ENTROPY (ΔS) DATA OF METAL HUMIC ACID COMPLEXES

Metal ion	T(°C)	- ΔG (KCal/mole)	ΔH (KCal/mole)	ΔS (Cal/deg/mole) at 30°C
Fe(III)	30	4.90	10.0	50.9
	40	5.43		
Al(III)	30	4.40	10.0	47.5
	40	4.84		
V(IV)	30	8.20	47.75	184.7
	40	10.03		
Ti(IV)	30	7.35	43.42	167.6
	40	9.03		
Mo(VI)	30	9.85	56.44	218.9
	40	12.02		

TABLE—3 FREE ENERGY (ΔG), ENTHALPY (ΔH) AND ENTROPY (ΔS) DATA FOR FULVIC ACID METAL COMPLEXES

Metal ion	T(°C)	$-\Delta G$ (KCal/mole)	ΔH (KCal/mole)	ΔS (Cal/deg/mole) at 30°C
Fe(III)	30	7.3	31.30	127.4
	40	8.6		
Al(III)	30	7.6	6.95	48.0
	40	8.1		
V(IV)	30	8.74	52.11	200.8
	40	10.75		
Ti(IV)	30	8.05	47.75	184.2
	40	9.90		
Mo(VI)	30	10.54	60.78	235.4
	40	12.90		

TABLE—4 FREE ENERGY (ΔG), ENTHALPY (ΔH) AND ENTROPY (ΔS) DATA FOR HYMATOMELANIC ACID METAL COMPLEXES

Metal ion	T(°C)	$-\Delta G$ (KCal/mole)	ΔH (KCal/mole)	ΔS (Cal/deg/mole) at 30°C
Fe(III)	30	5.50	41.7	155.8
	40	7.06		
Al(III)	30	5.3	4.5	60.0
	40	5.6		
V(IV)	30	5.7	39.0	147.5
	40	7.2		
Ti(IV)	30	5.27	30.40	117.7
	40	6.45		
Mo(VI)	30	7.7	34.73	140.0
	40	9.5		

The order of stability (Table 1) is Mo(VI) > V(IV) > Ti(IV) > Fe(III) > Al(III) which is justifiable on the basis that stability increases with increase in atomic number of the metal ions⁷. This is also justified from the point of view of ionic charge and ionic radius⁷. The increase in the values of stability constants with increase in temperature indicates that high temperature favours formation of stable complexes.

The results in Table (2) show a comparative picture of the values of free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) in different metal humic acid (HA) complexes. Similarly Tables (3) and (4) give results of the same for metal-fulvic acid (FA) and metal-hymatomelanic acid (HyA) complexes respectively. Comparison of these results show that

free energies of formation of V(IV), Ti(IV) and Mo(VI) complexes are high negative but in case of Fe(III) and Al(III) complexes these are of lower order. Moreover, it is also noticeable that the values are higher at 40° and lower at 30°. Such negative free energy change indicates spontaneity of complex formation. High negative values of ΔG in case of V(IV), Ti(IV) and Mo(VI) complexes indicate their greater complexing tendency with soil organic matter which thereby play a vital role in the micronutrients from soil to the plants.

The values of ΔH in all the cases are seen to be positive indicating absorption of energy during interaction.

The results of entropy change (ΔS) accompanying the formation of complexes are positive in all the cases thereby interpreting this chelation phenomena in soil as purely an entropy effect. The entropy change values are moderately high in almost all the cases except for Al(III) complexes. The gradual increase in the value of ΔS from Fe(III) to Mo(VI) complexes is also justified from the point of view of greater availability of coordination site in the metal ions as we proceed from first transition series to second or third series⁸. The remarkably low values of ΔG , ΔH and ΔS in case of Al(III) complexes is attributable to the so called "inert pair" effect⁹. From the more or less similar values of the thermodynamic parameters in case of different soil organic matter fractions, it may be inferred that metal ions remaining the same, the nature and stereochemistry of the different ligands used here appears to be almost identical. This view fully corroborates the observations made earlier from I.R. spectroscopic study of the same¹⁰.

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